

UNIVERSIDAD DE LAS PALMAS DE GRAN CANARIA
Instituto Universitario de Microelectrónica Aplicada

A SMART COMPRESSION APPROACH BASED ON THE CCSDS 123.0-B-2 STANDARD FOR CHIME

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- ▶ Context
- ▶ CHIME mission
- ▶ Cloud selective compression
- ▶ CCSDS 123.0-B-2 compression standard
- ▶ CCSDS 123.0-B-2 adaptation to CHIME
- ▶ Compression solution for CHIME
- ▶ Design optimizations
- ▶ Validation and implementation results
- ▶ Conclusions

- ▶ Use of Hyperspectral sensors in space and Earth Observation (EO) missions:
 - High data acquisition volume.
 - Limited HW resources and transmission bandwidth.
 - Hyperspectral data compression mandatory.
- ▶ Characteristic of EO missions: presence of clouds:
 - Clouds cover more than 50% Earth surface.
 - Presence of uninteresting regions in captured images.
 - Selective compression can be helpful.
- ▶ Copernicus Hyperspectral Imaging Mission for the Environment (CHIME):
 - Future space mission to complement COPERNICUS “Sentinels”.
 - Earth’s natural resources monitorization.
 - New services for food security, agriculture and raw materials.

- ▶ Hyperspectral sensor with 220 spectral bands in VNIR and SWIR domains
- ▶ Continuous data acquisitions at ~2 Gbps
 - Raw data memory volume in the order of Tbytes.
 - High volume of data => On-board Compression appears mandatory.
- ▶ Significant presence of Clouds in CHIME acquisitions:
 - Opaque Clouds are less useful to estimate Earth surface properties.
 - Possibilities to increase on-board data reduction through selective compression.
- ▶ Real-time processing constrains:
 - Throughput of 1 sample/clock cycle @125 MHz
 - Performance constraints not met by HLS pre-development^[1].
- ▶ CHIME Phase A/B1 pre-development financed by ESA
 - Collaboration among ULPGC, TASI5 and TASI6

[1] Y. Barrios, P. Rodríguez, A. Sánchez, M. González, L. Berrojo, and R. Sarmiento, "Implementation of Cloud Detection and Processing Algorithms and CCSDS-compliant Hyperspectral Image Compression for CHIME Mission", in OBPDC 2020

- ▶ Cloud detection stage before compression:
 - Based on Support Vector Machine (SVM)^[2].
 - Output: Cloud map. Indicates the class of each pixel (cloud: '1', ground: '0').
- ▶ Selective compression: CCSDS 123.0-B-2 compression standard with Different Absolute Error (DAE)^[2]:
 - Custom implementation (non-standard).
 - Different error settings for each pixel class (ground and cloud).
 - Losses based on current band and pixel class.

[2] D. Lebedeff, M. Foulon, R. Camarero, R. Vitulli, and Y. Bobichon, "On-board cloud detection and selective spatial/spectral compression based on the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 for hyperspectral missions", in OBPDC 2020

- ▶ An adaptive linear prediction method is used to predict the value of each image sample based on the values of nearby samples in a small three-dimensional neighbourhood.
- ▶ The quantizer step size can be controlled via an absolute error limit or a relative error limit (or both).
 - Lossless compression is obtained simply by setting the maximum error limit to zero.
- ▶ The quantized prediction residual $q_z(t)$ is mapped to an unsigned integer mapped quantizer index $\delta_z(t)$.
- ▶ Because of the introduction of losses, the predictor cannot work directly with the input samples.
 - Samples are reconstructed from the $q_z(t)$, in the same way as in the decompressor.
 - Sample representatives must be internally stored.
- ▶ 3 options for entropy coder: Sample-adaptive, Block-adaptive (CCSDS 121.0-B-3), and hybrid.
- ▶ Image ancillary data can be included through supplementary information tables.

► Data dependencies and computational complexity in predictor:

Lossless compression (CCSDS 123.0-B-1)
Weights feedback

Near-lossless compression (CCSDS 123.0-B-2)
Weights + sample representatives feedback

- Best processing order: BIP (Band-Interleaved by Pixel)
 - Weights dependency avoided.
 - 1 sample/clock cycle.

- BIP to be avoided.
- Preferred processing order: BIL (Band-Interleaved by Line)
- New compressor options to alleviate sample representatives dependency:
 - Narrow local sums + reduced prediction.
- Dependency on weights still there.
- Quantizer involves integer division.

► Implementation options:

- The CCSDS 123.0-B-2 standard has multiple configuration parameters influencing compression performance.
- Constrained option set to meet mission requirements.
- Samples order -> Band Interleaved by Line (BIL), whisk broom scanner.
- General predictor configuration values:

Parameter Name	Symbol	Allowed Values	Type
X size	N_x	[1:1536]	Dynamic
Y size	N_y	64	Static
Z size	N_z	[1:256]	Dynamic
Dynamic Range	D	16	Static
Number of Prediction Bands	P	3	Static
Local Sum Type		Narrow neighbour-oriented	Static
Prediction Mode		reduced	Static
Register Size	R	48	Static
Weight Component Resolution	Ω	19	Static
Weight Update Scaling Exponent Initial/Final Parameter	v_{min}, v_{max}	[-6:9]	Dynamic
Weight Update Scaling Exponent Change Interval	t_{inc}	$[2^8, 2^9, 2^{10}, 2^{11}]$	Dynamic

► Parameters related to near-lossless mode:

- Lossless compression is achieved by setting an all-zeroes error vector.

Parameter Name	Symbol	Allowed Values	Type
Quantizer Fidelity Control Method		Absolute error limit	Static
Absolute Error Limit Depth	D_A	Ground class: 8 Cloud class: 10	Static
Absolute Error Assignment Method		Band-dependent	Static
Sample Representative Resolution	Θ	4	Static
Sample Representative Offset/Damping	ψ_z, ϕ_z	[0:15]	Dynamic

► Entropy coder configuration parameters:

- Block-adaptive encoder is selected.

Parameter Name	Symbol	Allowed Values	Type
Block size	J	[32, 64]	Dynamic
Reference sample interval	r	4096	Static
Output Word size	B	4 (32 bits)	Static

- ▶ Extra parameters for cloud selective compression:
 - Cloud map + cloud errors.
 - Compression modes: 1-class or 2-classes.
 - Configuration ID: identifier for the combined set of configuration options (cloud detection + compression).
 - Use of supplementary information tables to ensure data self-containment.
 - Compression header:

Image metadata		Predictor metadata			Block coder metadata
Essential	Supplementary tables	Primary	Quantization (ground errors)	Sample representatives	

Table type	Table structure	Number of elements	Element size	Element type
Cloud map*	2-dimensional xy	$N_x \cdot N_y$	1	Unsigned integer
Cloud errors	1-dimensional	N_z	10	
Configuration ID	0-dimensional	1	32	

*User-defined data field denotes the compression mode (1-class or 2-classes)

▶ System overview:

- ▶ VHDL model.
 - ▶ Starting point: CCSDS 123.0-B-1 predictor.
 - ▶ Output interfaces compatible with entropy coder.
 - ▶ Interface with external memory for storing intermediate results.
 - ▶ Configuration through AMBA-AHB
- ▶ VHDL model developed in a previous work (SHyLoC CCSDS121-IP^[3]).
 - ▶ Widely verified with real and synthetic hyperspectral images
 - ▶ Configuration through AMBA-AHB.

[3] https://www.esa.int/Enabling_Support/Space_Engineering_Technology/Microelectronics/SHyLoC_IP_Core

- ▶ Near-lossless predictor overview:
 - Config core receives configuration from AHB and generates compression header (image + predictor metadata).
 - To be completed by block-coder.
 - Cloud map received twice:
 - For header generation (Is header = '1'): through Input samples port.
 - During compression (Is header = '0'): accompanying each input sample through Cloud flag side input.
 - Interface with external memory for storing intermediate results

► Near-lossless predictor architecture:

- BIL processing order.
- External memory acts as a large FIFO for sample representatives.
- Cloud flags are propagated along input samples.
 - Error limit determined by cloud flags.
- Pipeline with II=1.
- Optimizations applied:
 - Mitigate weights dependency.
 - Integer division implementation.

► Reducing weights dependency:

- Alternative way of computing $\text{sgn}^+[e_z(t)]$ ^[4]:
 - Feedback loop reduced.
 - Quantizer out of the feedback loop.
- Eager computation^[4]:
 - Consider both values of $\text{sgn}^+[e_z(t)]$ in parallel and take decisions later.

Both strategies combined allow to reach $||=1$

[4] A. Sánchez, I. Blanes, Y. Barrios, M. Hernández-Cabronero, J. Bartrina-Rapesta, J. Serra-Sagrìstà and R. Sarmiento, "Reducing Data Dependencies in the Feedback Loop of the CCSDS 123.0-B-2 Predictor", IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters © (under-review)

▶ Integer division implementation

- In near-lossless compression mode, divisions by non-power of 2 are applied.
- All divisions (quantizer + mapper) share the same denominator.
- Proposal: compute division as multiplication with pre-computed inverse denominator.
 - Prone to rounding errors. Proper rounding and resolution are required.

$$\frac{|\Delta_z| + m_z(t)}{2 \cdot m_z(t) + 1} = (|\Delta_z| + m_z(t)) \cdot \frac{1}{2 \cdot m_z(t) + 1}$$

- ▶ Pre-computed inverse denominators are stored in a BRAM.
 - Addressed with $m_z(t)$.
- ▶ Multiplication must fit the Xilinx KU040/060 DSP resources:
 - Operand sizes: $\leq 18 \times 27$ bits.
 - Error limit depth: $D_A \leq 10$ bits.

- ▶ Validation set:
 - Images generated by OPSI simulator.
 - 5 full images (5 hyperspectral cubes x 64 lines each)
 - Each image has its own cloud map.
 - Set of small slices to test a wider range of configuration sets.
 - Total: 57 test cases.
- ▶ Golden reference: software implementation of the custom CCSDS 123.0-B-2 with DAE approach.
- ▶ Configuration sets within the boundaries defined for CHIME compression solution.
- ▶ All tests were successful.

► Implementation results:

- Target part: Xilinx Kintex UltraScale XQKU060-1i.
- Synthesis tool: Synopsys Synplify Premier P-2019.09-SP1.
- Implementation tool: Xilinx Vivado 2019.1.

RESOURCE	CHIME PREDICTOR	CCSDS121-IP (BLOCK-ADAPTIVE ENCODER)	TOTAL
BRAM_18K	8 (0.7%)	3 (0.3%)	11 (1.0%)
DSP48E	37 (1.3%)	5 (0.2%)	42 (1.5%)
FF	4926 (0.7%)	2085 (0.3%)	7011 (1.0%)
LUT	8492 (2.6%)	5904 (1.8%)	14396 (4.4%)
Clock freq. (MHz)	125.2	125.7	125.2

- Throughput: 1 sample/clock cycle.
- Maximum clock frequency: 125.2 MHz (after P&R).

- ▶ Compression solution for CHIME mission proposed, comprised by:
 - Custom CCSDS 123.0-B-2 pre-processor with DAE.
 - SHyLoC 2.0 121 IP (Block-adaptive entropy coder compliant with CCSDS 121.0-B-3).
- ▶ Cloud selective compression:
 - Cloud map is generated prior to compression, denoting the class of each pixel.
 - Degree of quantization depends on pixel class.
 - Data self-containment: use of CCSDS 123 supplementary information tables to encode non-standard parameters (cloud map, cloud error vector).
- ▶ Proposed design meets mission requirements: 1 sample/clock cycle @125 MHz
- ▶ Design optimizations:
 - Mitigation of data dependencies.
 - Integer division implementation.
- ▶ Validation campaign successful.
- ▶ Implementation results on XQKU060-1i

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